

PROBLEMATIC QUESTIONS TO PREPARE YOUNG PEOPLE TO THE CALL

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Annotation: the article tells about the training process, in which pre-conscription training is planned in every possible way, under pedagogical control, its main task is to arm the guys with the necessary knowledge and skills to form their spiritual, mental and physical training for military service, to become a real defender of military service. The main task, role and significance of the formation of spiritual and mental and physical self-esteem for military service in young people, their armament with the knowledge and skills necessary for a true defender of the Fatherland were spoken of.

Keywords: preparedness to the call, military-patriotism, Homeland, society, heroism, courage, Law, Justice, love for the motherland, loyalty.

In a situation where military science and technology are developing rapidly, international terrorism and the threat of religious extremism are growing, the comprehensive training of young people for military service is becoming more and more important, it is necessary to further improve military service, look for new ways, forms and methods. it depends on the joint efforts of its organization and government bodies, ministries and departments, which are agreed.

"Pre-draft training is a comprehensively planned, pedagogically supervised educational process, the main task of which is to arm the guys with the necessary knowledge and skills to form their spiritual, mental and physical training for military service, to become a real defender of military service. It is the main task in the guys to form a spiritual and spiritual and physical essence for military service, to arm them with the knowledge and skills necessary for a true defender of the Fatherland."

Pre-draft training does not make it a goal to make a ready-made soldier from a guy. Even in a few weeks, a soldier can be trained to a minimum, providing basic knowledge and skills in military affairs. But even in weeks, even months, it is impossible to instill in it a sense of conscious readiness to serve the motherland faithfully. The increase in the role of training before conscription is also determined by the influence of scientific and technological progress on the development of military affairs.

Despite the fact that in the years of independence, a lot of modern, comprehensively equipped and equipped buildings were erected in our country for vocational colleges, a training and material base for pre-conscription training (ChQT) was not created in them. Obstacle courses, no firing ranges built, no organization and conduct of training and tactical training, no fields for the study of guard duties (hours), daily shifts, no firing guns, no rooms for the storage of training mines. Grenades, etc., which are mandatory elements for organizing and conducting training on ChQT.

On the basis of the law of our country "on General military duty and military service", since the 2017-2018 academic year, primary military training has been resumed as a mandatory

subject of general secondary education in schools. In the last 20 years after the cessation of education in grades 10-11, all the outdated educational and material base of the Chqt was partially transferred to secondary special educational institutions and was considered obsolete. Weapons storage rooms, shooting galleries, barrier crossings and other obsolete unusable material bases designed to organize and conduct Chqt were destroyed, to put it mildly, due to the lack of need. Only a year later, only from the 2018-2019 school year, schools were provided with chqt textbooks and a few posters.

An analysis of the real state of affairs on the preparation of young people to term military conscription shows that there are certain problems that prevent young people from gaining full and high-quality knowledge. This is the imperfection of regulatory legal acts that do not correspond to reality, the lack of material and technical support, the lack of a material and technical base, as well as the lack of adequate pedagogical personnel qualifications, the absence of the necessary conditions for organizing and conducting classes. .

The Ministry of Defense, together with the interested ministries and departments, needs to develop and adopt a unified concept of preparing the youth of our country for term military service.

In connection with the revival of general secondary education in schools, it is necessary to make amendments to the current “pre-draft regulations” in 2014.

Considering the presence of an external and internal threat to national security, it is necessary to make adjustments to the ChQT program, because, in practice, since 1992, school, college and academic lyceums do not have small-caliber rifles, training machines, training mines, grenades, etc.

It will be advisable to re-establish the activities of Defense sports recreation camps, which are provided with a modern material and technical base in regional centers and the city of Tashkent, with all kinds of weapons and necessary training equipment. Including barracks and other necessary attributes of military service.

This, in turn, frees the commanders of military units in the field from endless “guests” and serves to work on their own – to carry out combat missions to guard and defend the borders of the state, to conduct combat and political training with personal composition.

Students of Defense sports wellness camps should fully study the firearm training departments of ChQT science, the basics of military affairs and practical physical training (for example: overcoming obstacles and hand-to-hand combat techniques), get acquainted with the agenda, the life and life of military units, feel the severity of military service for at least a few days. This makes it possible to raise initial military training to a high level of quality.

The problem of the shortage of teachers in the subject of primary military training in secondary special educational institutions was partially solved at the expense of the full maintenance of pensions of armed forces pensioners who worked in the positions of head of educational institutions (deputy leaders), teachers (teachers) of military personnel. initial military training of Republican academic lyceums and vocational colleges. This measure was very effective during the opening of grades 10-11 in schools. Many vacancies in educational institutions were filled by Reserve Officers with extensive experience in the life of the army.

At the same time, to the practically large experience of officers from the reserve, children, pedagogical skills in working with upper-class students of educational institutions are not sufficiently formed, there is no practice of planning educational activities. process, they do not

have modern innovative pedagogical technologies. In order to improve their pedagogical skills, it is necessary, first of all, to carry out qualitative and timely 5-day educational and methodological meetings of military personnel during the winter and summer holidays of students, to popularize advanced experiments, to carry out Control and leadership.

But far from military work in the provincial public education departments and secondary special education departments, individuals who cannot control the activities of ChQT teachers are often appointed Methodists in charge of the Chqt. The heads of the Departments of pre-conscription training of young men under the Departments of defense affairs are systematically involved in warning term servicemen, charging employees of the Ministry of Natural Resources and performing various current tasks of the Departments of defense affairs. In order to carry out effective leadership and control over the activities of ChQT leaders (teachers), it is advisable to introduce official officer states in the Departments of defense affairs of cities and districts, to increase the demand and demand for their positions. regular officers.

In general, classes are held only in theory, not specified in practical classes. There is no comprehensive development of all elements of training before the draft. In each educational institution, it is necessary to create an educational and material and technical base in accordance with annex 4-8 of the "pre-call preliminary training program" approved by the order of the Ministry of higher and secondary special education.

Today, due to the limitation of educational institutions with textbooks, visual aids, posters, the educational process in them remains at the level of narrative and superficial acquaintance.

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